

DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF BILIARY TRACT ULTRASOUND IN
DIAGNOSIS OF CAUSE OF OBSTRUCTIVE JAUNDICE KEEPING
MAGNETIC RESONANCE CHOLANGIOPANCREATICOGRAPHY (MRCP)
AS GOLD STANDARD

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Abstract

Objectives: To assess the accuracy of ultrasound of biliary tract to determine the cause of obstructive jaundice by comparing with MRCP considered as the gold standard.

Study design: Cross-sectional (validation) study.

Place and Duration of the study: Combined Military Hospital, Rawalpindi from February 2024 to July 2024.

Methodology: A total of 294 patients with obstructive jaundice were included. They were assessed for the cause of their condition first by ultrasonography of their biliary tree followed by MRCP and whether the cause was identified or not was documented, in addition to the cause itself. Causes were stratified by confounding variables and post-stratification comparison was performed using Chi-square test. 2x2 contingency tables were drawn to calculate diagnostic accuracy parameters.

Results: In this study, 294 patients were included. Median age was 45.00 (19.00) years. There were 146 (49.70%) male and 148 (50.30%) female patients. Median weight was 78.00 (52.00) kg. Median duration of having jaundice was 4.00 (4.00) weeks. On ultrasound, obstructive jaundice cause was identified in 194 (66.00%) patients while on MRCP, cause was identified in 246 (83.70%) of the patients. Based on these findings, sensitivity was calculated to be at 77.24%, specificity at 91.67%, accuracy at 79.59%, positive predictive value at 97.94% and negative predictive value at 44.00%.

Conclusion: Ultrasound of biliary tree can identify cause of obstructive jaundice in most instances with an accuracy of 79.59%.

INTRODUCTION

Obstructive jaundice refer to yellowish discolouration of sclera and skin secondary to extra-hepatic or intra-hepatic mechanical obstruction of biliary flow through the biliary tract. ¹Characteristically, when the jaundice is of obstructive variety, it is generally quite

severe and patients often have concomitant itching due to excessive accumulation of bilirubin. ² This particular type of jaundice can occur due to a wide variety of reasons which can be as benign as a stone in the duct draining the bile and can be as life

threatening as the malignancy.³ Regarding the tumorous causes of this particular jaundice type, some of the usually reported pathologies are carcinoma of gall bladder, cholangiocarcinoma, carcinoma of head of pancreas, carcinoma of periampullary region and the benign common bile duct stricture.⁴

When it comes to the prevalence of the obstructive type of jaundice, it has been observed that globally, this jaundice type makes up around 17-18% of all the cases of jaundice making up almost five cases per one thousand cases of jaundice.^{5,6} To diagnose cause of obstructive jaundice, magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) has been considered highly useful and studies have reported high level of diagnostic accuracy of this investigations in determining cause of obstructive jaundice.⁷ In fact, according to the data from a previous study it was found that MRCP provided a detection rate of the pathology behind the causation of obstructive jaundice ranging from 90% to 100% making it highly accurate.⁷

However, this advanced radiological diagnostic modality is not frequently available in many health care facilities in resource limited countries like Pakistan and radiologists have to rely on readily available modalities, like ultrasonography, to determine cause of obstructive jaundice prior to therapeutic intervention.⁸ Although, literature exhibits a correlation between the aforementioned diagnostic modalities to diagnose the obstructive jaundice cause, yet a high degree of variability exists when it comes to ability of ultrasound, compared to MRCP, to diagnose obstructive jaundice cause. Therefore, present study was conducted with the aim to address this variation in the previous literature and find the accuracy of ultrasound of biliary tract to determine the cause of obstructive jaundice by comparing with MRCP considered as the gold standard.

METHODOLOGY

This cross sectional (validation) study was conducted at CMH, Rawalpindi from February 2024 to July 2024. Sample size calculation was performed using sensitivity and specificity sample size calculator by assuming a confidence level of 95%, precision of 10%, prevalence of obstructive jaundice of 17.1%⁵, expected sensitivity of 84.57%⁹ and expected

specificity of 79.10%.⁹ This yielded a sample size of 294 which was selected by using non-probability consecutive sampling technique.

Patients aged 16 – 65 years of either gender, who presented with obstructive jaundice were included. Jaundiced patients were labeled to have obstructive type of jaundice if there was presence clinically evident jaundice along with serum bilirubin more than 1.2mg/dl and cholestatic pattern of liver enzymes characterised by normal aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine transaminase (ALT) with markedly raised alkaline phosphatase (ALP). Patients with any contraindication to MRCP (like metallic implants in body or claustrophobia), raised AST and ALT, history of bone, renal or liver disease and pregnant women were excluded.

Obtaining of informed consent in written form was made prerequisite before inclusion in the study. Baseline characteristics including age (in years), gender, weight (in kilograms) and duration of having jaundice (in weeks) were documented. After that patients underwent biliary tract ultrasound to establish a provisional diagnosis of the cause of obstructive jaundice and its results were documented in a pre-approved, predesigned data collection proforma. After that, all the patients underwent MRCP for confirmation of cause. Based on the final findings of ultrasound and MRCP, case allocation was performed. Cases were labeled as true positives (TP) if ultrasound of the biliary tract and MRCP were able to identify the cause. Cases were labeled as true negatives (TN) if ultrasound as well as MRCP were unable to identify any cause. Cases were labeled as false positives (FP) if cause of obstruction of the biliary tree was identifiable with ultrasound but not with the MRCP. Cases were labeled as false negatives (FN) if ultrasound was unable to distinguish any specific cause of the biliary tract obstruction but it was identified with the help of MRCP.

Data was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22. Quantitative variables (age, weight and duration of having jaundice) were presented as median interquartile range (IQR) after checking normality of data by Shapiro-Wilk test which showed that these were not distributed normally. Qualitative variables (gender and cause) was presented as frequency and percentages. 2×2 contingency table was drawn in order to calculate values of diagnostic

accuracy parameters as per their respective formulae. Causes were stratified by age, gender, weight and duration of having jaundice and post-stratification comparison was performed using Chi-square test. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS

In this study, 60 patients were included. Median age was 45.00 (19.00) years. There were 146 (49.70%) male and 148 (50.30%) female patients. Median weight was 78.00 (52.00) kg. Median duration of having jaundice was 4.00 (4.00) weeks. Patient demographics are further elaborated in Table-I:

Table-I: Patients demographics (n = 294)

Demographic variable	Median (IQR); n (%)
Age	45.00 (19.00) years
< 40 years	97 (33.00%)
≥ 40 years	197 (67.00%)
Gender	
Male	146 (49.70%)
Female	148 (50.30%)
Weight	78.00 (52.00) kg
< 70 kg	134 (45.60%)
≥ 70 kg	160 (54.40%)
Duration of having jaundice	4.00 (4.00) weeks
< 4 weeks	141 (48.00%)
≥ 4 weeks	153 (52.00%)

Abbreviations: IQR = Interquartile range, n = number of patients, kg = kilograms
 On ultrasound, obstructive jaundice cause was identified in 194 (66.00%) patients while no cause was identified in 100 (34.00%) patients. On MRCP, cause was identified in 246 (83.70%) of the patients

while no cause was found in 48 (16.30%) patients. Based on these findings, TP, TN, FP and FN cases were identified which are given in Table-II. Based on these, diagnostic accuracy parameters were calculated which are also given in Table-II:

Table-II: 2x2 contingency table of cases distribution and diagnostic accuracy variables of ultrasound to diagnose cause of obstructive jaundice (n = 294)

	Cause identified on MRCP	No cause identified on MRCP
Cause identified on USG	190 (TP)	4 (FP)
No cause identified on USG	56 (FN)	44 (TN)
Diagnostic accuracy parameters		
Sensitivity	77.24%	
Specificity	91.67%	
Accuracy	79.59%	
PPV	97.94%	
NPV	44.00%	

Abbreviations: USG = Ultrasound, MRCP = Magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography, TP = True positive, FP = False positive, FN = False negative, TN = True negative, PPV = Positive predictive value, NPV = Negative predictive value

Most common causative aetiology that led to development of jaundice of obstructive type was choledocholithiasis found in 122 (41.50%) patients followed by gallbladder carcinoma in 44 (15.00%) patients, malignant stricture in 42 (14.30%) patients, pancreatic carcinoma in 19 (6.50%) patients and

Mirizzi syndrome in 19 (6.50%) patients. Stratification of frequency of causes by age, gender,

weight and duration of having jaundice is given in Table-III:

Table-III: Stratification of frequency of causes by confounding variables (n =294)

Age stratification			
Cause	< 40 years (n = 97)	≥ 40 years (n = 197)	p-value
Choledocholithiasis	35 (36.08%)	87 (44.16%)	0.357†
Gallbladder carcinoma	14 (14.43%)	30 (15.23%)	
Malignant stricture	17 (17.53%)	25 (12.69%)	
Pancreatic carcinoma	6 (6.19%)	13 (6.60%)	
Mirizzi syndrome	10 (10.31%)	9 (4.57%)	
No cause identified	15 (15.46%)	33 (16.75%)	
Gender stratification			
Cause	Male (n = 146)	Female (n = 148)	p-value
Choledocholithiasis	64 (43.84%)	58 (39.19%)	0.246†
Gallbladder carcinoma	22 (15.07%)	22 (14.86%)	
Malignant stricture	15 (10.27%)	27 (18.24%)	
Pancreatic carcinoma	10 (6.85%)	9 (6.08%)	
Mirizzi syndrome	13 (8.90%)	6 (4.05%)	
No cause identified	22 (15.07%)	26 (17.57%)	
Weight stratification			
Cause	< 70 kg (n = 134)	≥ 70 kg (n = 160)	p-value
Choledocholithiasis	29 (21.64%)	93 (58.13%)	< 0.001†
Gallbladder carcinoma	33 (24.63%)	11 (6.88%)	
Malignant stricture	39 (29.10%)	3 (1.88%)	
Pancreatic carcinoma	10 (7.46%)	9 (5.63%)	
Mirizzi syndrome	7 (5.22%)	12 (7.50%)	
No cause identified	16 (11.94%)	32 (20.00%)	
Stratification of duration for having jaundice			
Cause	< 4 weeks (n = 141)	≥ 4 weeks (n = 153)	p-value
Choledocholithiasis	46 (32.62%)	76 (49.67%)	0.006†
Gallbladder carcinoma	21 (14.89%)	23 (15.03%)	
Malignant stricture	26 (18.44%)	16 (10.48%)	
Pancreatic carcinoma	15 (10.64%)	4 (2.61%)	
Mirizzi syndrome	8 (5.67%)	11 (7.19%)	
No cause identified	25 (17.73%)	23 (15.03%)	

† Chi-square test

DISCUSSION

Present study focused on an important diagnostic aspect of jaundice secondary to the flow restriction in the biliary tract, keeping in view the underdeveloped status of Pakistan and paucity of availability of the modern diagnostic modalities, which play an essential role in effective non-invasive diagnosis.^{10,11} In present study, average age of the patients who presented with this pathology was forty-five years with majority of

patients belonged to the older age group constituting 67% of the total population. Possible reason behind this trend is higher risk of having the common benign condition (like choledocholithiasis) and malignancy of the biliary tract being associated with advancing and older age.^{12,13}

Upon analysis of the gender distribution, it was observed that female jaundiced patients were slightly more in number compared to male patients. Similar

to this, a study conducted by Alshoabi *et al.*¹⁴ analysed the demographic trends of obstructive jaundice and found a slight female predominance in this regard. Similarly, in another study conducted by Sahu *et al.*¹⁵ this slight female predominance in having this particular jaundice type with a ratio of males to females of 0.91. One possible reason for this female predominance is the higher propensity of women to develop stones in their biliary tract, thereby, exposing them to develop this condition.^{16, 17}

Upon analysis of the cause of this condition, most common non-tumorous aetiological cause was choledocholithiasis occurring in 41.5% of the patients while the most common malignant cause was gallbladder carcinoma accounting for 15% of the cases. Similar to this, a study was conducted by Murshid *et al.*¹⁸ in which it was found that among non-tumorous causes, there was complete agreement with present study with choledocholithiasis topping the aetiology leaderboard but regarding the malignant causes there was a slight difference with pancreatic cancer being the leading aetiology. This difference may have occurred due to demographic differences of the distribution of various malignancies in various regions of the world.

When the impact of various confounding variables on the aetiological spectrum of obstructive jaundice was analysed, it was found that although age and gender had no significant impact but a significant impact was exerted by the weight of patient at the time of diagnosis and the duration for which patient was having jaundice. It was seen that patients with non-tumorous aetiology, belonged to group with higher weight while those with lower weight were more likely to have malignant aetiology. This is explainable by the association of higher body weight and increased chances of having gallstones and the association of cachexia with ongoing malignancy.^{19, 20}

Upon analysis of the diagnostic accuracy parameters of the biliary tract ultrasound for finding cause of obstructive jaundice it was found that values for sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and accuracy were 77.24%, 91.67%, 97.94%, 44.00% and 79.59%, respectively. One study conducted by Saeed *et al.*²¹ reported the values of the aforementioned diagnostic accuracy parameters of biliary tract ultrasound to diagnose this condition at 86.84%, 77.78%, 92.52%, 65.12% and 84.67%, respectively. Another study

conducted by Debbarma *et al.*²² found that biliary tract ultrasound was found to be much more sensitive compared to present study with a reported sensitivity of 97% while the specificity of this investigation was much lower (at 67%) in their study compared to present study. Similarly, accuracy reported by Debbarma *et al.*²² of biliary tract ultrasound to diagnose the cause of jaundice of obstructive type was also much higher, reported at 97.4%, compared to present study. In one study conducted by Swaraj *et al.*²³ found that sensitivity, specificity and accuracy of biliary tract ultrasound to identify cause of obstructive jaundice, compared with MRCP, was very low and was reported at merely 33.3%, 84% and 48.9%, respectively. The exact reason for this variability was not identified but one possible reason is the difference in the type of ultrasound machine and expertise of sonologist between current and past studies.

Based on the results of present study, it is evident that biliary tract ultrasound is a highly reliable tool that can effectively diagnose obstructive jaundice cause and can be used as a reliable alternative to MRCP at places where this facility is not available. There were no limitations of present study.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, biliary tract ultrasound can identify cause of obstructive jaundice in most instances with a high level of accuracy of 79.59%.

ETHICAL APPROVAL:

Obtained from the hospital ethical committee of CMH, Rawalpindi (Ref No: ERC/631/23).

PATIENTS' CONSENT:

Informed consent in writing was taken from all participants.

COMPETING INTEREST:

None.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION:

Maham Saqib and Javed Anwar drafting of work, design analysis, data acquisition data interpretation and approval of final version to be published.

Muhammad Ali, Amna Shahid and Aimen Hafeez data analysis, data acquisition, critical revision and approval of final version to be published.

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